

AI Horizons: Navigating the Future of Social Sciences and Finance Education (AIH)

Version 1

Description

DMP describes the strategy for gathering, processing, publishing, organizing, and storing the data related to the project "AI Horizons: Navigating the Future of Social Sciences and Finance Education (AIH)" (Nr. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0034)

Project aims:

(1) Evaluate Pedagogical Approaches with Generative AI in higher education of social sciences and finance: The project aims to identify and analyze effective pedagogical strategies tailored for the inclusion of generative AI in social sciences and finance education. It will investigate how generative AI can enhance traditional teaching approaches and create more dynamic and participative learning environments.

(2) Assess the use of generative AI by Educators and Students: The project will also explore how both educators and students at the University of Latvia and The School of Business and Finance currently integrate generative AI into their educational frameworks. This will include identifying existing practices, usage gaps, and pinpoint opportunities for enhancing the use of AI tools in educational settings.

(3) Synthesis and Dissemination of Insights: The project will conclude with synthesizing the research findings into actionable knowledge and disseminating it across various platforms to impact wider educational practices in both higher education institutions. This includes the academic community and beyond, aiming to refine AI integration strategies in education.

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Funded by Recovery and Resilience Facility project "Internal and External Consolidation of the University of Latvia" (No.5.2.1.1.i.0/2/24/I/CFLA/007).

Researchers

Normunds Gruzitis (0000-0003-0511-1829), Visvaldis Valtenbergs (0000-0001-6276-7475), Linda Daniela (0000-0002-0712-2276), Jānis Ikstens (0000-0003-3191-6305), Aivars Spilbergs (0000-0003-2537-8053), Ieva Matjola (0009-0004-4060-9141), Raivis Viluns (0000-0002-6294-7895), Velta Skolmeistere (0000-0002-3704-4547)

Organizations

University of Latvia, BA School of Business and Finance

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [AI Horizons: Navigating the Future of Social Sciences and Finance Education \(AIH\)](#)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: European Commission | EC

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Project: "AI Horizons: Navigating the Future of Social Sciences and Finance Education (AIH)", Nr. LU-BA-PA-2024/1-0034

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

Publication Date: 2024-11-30

4. Templates

Descriptions

Use of artificial intelligence among the students of the University of Latvia

The dataset consists of survey data gathered in 2025. Students of the University of Latvia are questioned in order to find out the practices of using artificial intelligence to facilitate the study process.

Template: LCS FARP

Type: Dataset

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The pilot study aims to engage purposefully selected groups of undergraduate and

graduate students, from the UL representing various sub-disciplines within social sciences who possess prior some or considerable prior experience with generative AI tools. Building upon a previous qualitative phase, insights gathered will inform the design of succinct online questionnaires tailored for both students and educators. These questionnaires will be distributed via university email channels within UL, facilitating a wider engagement with the student population. This survey phase is structured to capture a broader spectrum of perspectives and experiences, enabling a more comprehensive examination of the implications of generative AI tools on teaching and learning practices within the context of social sciences and finance education. The data will be subjected to descriptive statistical analysis to summarize and present key characteristics and trends within the dataset. Factor analysis may be employed to identify underlying factors or latent variables that explain the patterns of responses across different survey questions.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- SAV

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

There are no previous data relevant to the subject.

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

Data will be useful for social scientists investigating the usage of AI in higher education.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

- DOI
- URL

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

Zenodo

<https://zenodo.org/>

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

SPSS is needed for .sav files.

For .csv, no specific software is required.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Velta Skolmeistere

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Use of artificial intelligence among the students of the BA School of Business and Finance

The dataset consists of survey data gathered in 2025. Students of the BA School of Business and Finance are questioned in order to find out the practices of using artificial intelligence to facilitate the study process.

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